

Intersection of Culture and Entrepreneurship: A Critical Analysis of how Sociocultural Environment Influences Women Entrepreneurial Growth in Delta State.

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Abstract: *Over the years, the desire for women to build careers in entrepreneurship has been negatively impacted by social structure, values and gender socialization. This study examined the influence of sociocultural environment on women entrepreneurial growth in Delta State. Sample was drawn from 392 respondents who operate diverse businesses within Delta State. Using a quantitative method, data was collected through structured surveys measuring cultural norm, social network, and growth of women entrepreneurs. Statistical analysis revealed significant positive correlations between cultural norm ($r = 0.54, p < 0.01$), social network ($r = 0.63, p < 0.001$), with increased growth of women entrepreneurs. Based on the findings the study recommends that cultural norms that support women entrepreneurship should be encouraged through the abolishment of traditional stereotypes and biases that limit women entrepreneurial potential and collaboration alongside knowledge-sharing among women entrepreneurs should be encouraged through the establishment of networks that provide support, mentorship, and resources for women entrepreneurs.*

Keywords: sociocultural, women entrepreneurship, cultural norm, social network and entrepreneurial growth.

Introduction

Entrepreneurship has been recognized as a significant driver of economic development and growth in a country (Dabbous, Barakat, & Kraus, 2023). Studies have shown how entrepreneurial activities contribute significantly to employment creation and growth in modern society (Emon & Nipa, 2024; Dabbous, Barakat, & Kraus, 2023). The contributions of women entrepreneurs towards sustainable economic growth cannot be overemphasized (Ajani, Gamede & Mkhasibe, 2021). Women are vital to entrepreneurship and economic progress (Kelley, Baumer, Brush, Greene, Mahdavi, Majbouri, & Heavlow, 2017). Unfortunately, Research have shown that women entrepreneurs are more responsive to gender stereotypes which emanate from culture than male entrepreneurs (Anggadwita, Luturlean, Ramadani & Ratten, 2017). Women all over the world exhibit similar features in terms of how institutional arrangements define their position in society in which culture, class, race, among several others, shape their roles in society (Anggadwita, Luturlean, Ramadani & Ratten, 2017).

Over the years, the desire for women to build careers in entrepreneurship has been negatively impacted by social structure, values and gender socialization/stereotypes (Adom, & Anambane, 2020). However, the past 30 decades have witnessed a rise in women venturing in entrepreneurship (Adom, & Anambane, 2020). Irrespective of this rise, women entrepreneurs are still faced with unique challenges and opportunities shaped by sociocultural factors which either promote or constrain their business growth (Uddin, 2021). Traditional gender roles and societal expectations often limit women's participation in business activities, confining them to specific industries or roles deemed appropriate for their gender. In addition, sociocultural constraints restrict women's ability to participate in professional networks, which are crucial for mentorship, knowledge sharing, and business development.

Delta State, with its distinctive sociocultural characteristics, provides an engrossing context for analyzing the effects of sociocultural environment on women entrepreneurs. This focus is critical because many women in this region operate within informal sectors that are vital to local economies yet remain underrepresented in scholarly research. Most existing studies on entrepreneurial growth in Nigeria address broad national trends or focus on urban centers, often neglecting the region-specific dynamics that influence entrepreneurship in the country (Kidiri, Alasan, kolo, Akinde & Owoniya, 2024).

While the impact of external business environment towards the growth of women entrepreneurs has been documented (kidiri, Alasan, kolo, Akinde & Owoniya, 2024), there still exists a gap. There is need to carry out further research on how sociocultural environment affect women entrepreneurs in Delta State, Nigeria. Addressing this gap is essential for designing targeted policies and interventions to support the growth of women-led businesses in the region. This study aims to examine the influence of sociocultural environment on women entrepreneurial growth in Delta State, Nigeria. The specific objective is to assess the impact of cultural norm and social network on women entrepreneurial growth in Delta State. By identifying the sociocultural factors that shape women entrepreneurial experiences, this study will provide actionable insights for stakeholders, including development agencies, policymakers, and financial institutions to foster a more supportive and enabling business environment for women entrepreneurs in Delta State.

Literature Review

Conceptual framework

This study is built on the assumptions conceptualized below

Figure 1: Conceptual framework of Sociocultural Environment and Women Entrepreneurial Growth.

Source: Constructed by the Researcher, 2025.

Figure 1 summarizes the effects of sociocultural environment on women entrepreneurial growth showing the direct and indirect link between the variables.

Concept of Women Entrepreneurship

Women entrepreneurship has become a key driving force for economic development and wealth creation and has been identified as an important ‘untapped source’ for economic growth and development (Adom & Anambane, 2020). Dabić, Dana, Nziku & Ramadani, (2022) stated that women entrepreneurs contribute to the economic well-being of countries by reducing poverty and increasing the overall level of family income, which leads to better education and healthy living. In developing countries, women entrepreneurs are deemed as “rising stars” and the “new instruments” for growth of economies (Adom, 2023). This is because they are taking leading roles in establishing and developing noteworthy enterprises that contribute significantly to poverty reduction and job creation (Emon & Nipa, 2024).

According to Rashid & Ratten, (2020), women entrepreneurship includes activities such as identifying market opportunities, managing new ventures, and pursuing economic and social objectives. These efforts are often shaped by a combination of individual traits, cultural influences, and institutional frameworks. Dixit, Malik, Seth & Sethi, (2023) further highlight that women entrepreneurs focus on organizing resources and building businesses to achieve financial independence, empowerment, and social impact.

However, women have been found to have lower opportunities for entrepreneurship (Ughetto, Rossi, Audretsch & Lehmann, 2020). Lapuente & Suzuki, (2021) stated that Women entrepreneurs tend to be more risk averse and less innovative than their male counterparts and this limits the growth opportunities of their enterprises. Although,

this depends on the culture and tradition of the entrepreneur as some cultures supports risk-taking and women within such cultures are less afraid of failure. Even so, Adom & Anambane, (2020) stated that the value placed on traditions in most African cultures is a bane to the growth and expansion of female-owned enterprises.

Sociocultural Environment

Sociocultural environment refers to the societal and cultural factors that shape the behaviors, values, norms, and practices within a community or society (Chernukha, Petrova, Vasylieva-Khalatnykova, Krupnyk & Krasilova, (2021). It encompasses elements such as language, religion, customs, values, education, family structure, and social norms, all of which influence how individuals and groups interact and function in society. These elements collectively affect economic behavior, decision-making, and development playing a critical role in shaping economic outcomes (Fahrati, (2023). According to Dumchak, Kachmar, Mochalova, Oleksandrenko & Sidorova, (2024), sociocultural environment strongly influences the quality and accessibility of education, which directly impacts human capital development. Societies that value education and invest in it tend to see higher levels of productivity and innovation.

However, while the sociocultural environment positively influence economic growth, it has the propensity to produce negative implications for economic development (Méndez-Picazo, Galindo-Martín & Castaño-Martínez, 2021). Certain aspects of the sociocultural environment such as social norms, cultural resistance to change and systemic inequalities hinders economic growth by stifling innovation, limiting human potential and creating barriers to trade and investment (Mohamamdali, 2023).

Thus, in the context of this study, emphasis is on cultural norm and social network as factors of the sociocultural environment.

Cultural norm

Culture has long been linked to entrepreneurship, stemming back all the way to Weber's work on the Protestant work ethic (Hollow, 2022). According to (Wikipedia, 2025), cultural norm refer to the shared values, beliefs and practices that are accepted and expected within a particular cultural group. These norms serve as guidelines for behavior, influencing how individuals interact with each other and their environment. Cultural norm either support or hinders the growth of entrepreneurship depending on the specific norms and values prevalent in a society (Chowdhury, 2024).

In Nigeria, Cultural norms significantly influence the entrepreneurial journeys of women, affecting their motivations, opportunities, and business growth (Adiza, Alamina, & Aliyu, 2020). In many societies, traditional gender roles often designate women primarily as caregivers, limiting their participation in business activities (Tseer, Suaka, & Awinpoka Akurugu, 2025). This societal expectation lead to feeling of isolation among female entrepreneurs as they navigate biases and stereotypes in environments where women in business are rare. The scarcity of female role models further exacerbates this challenge, making it difficult for aspiring women entrepreneurs to find mentors and support networks (Rehman, & Qamar, (2024).

Moreover, cultural perceptions of entrepreneurship as a masculine endeavor impact women's self-perception and ambition in business. Study by Martiarena, (2022) have shown that women who identify with feminine traits may have lower growth expectations for their businesses, especially in industries where female participation is minimal. This internalization of gender stereotypes influences their business strategies and limit their aspirations (Adapa, Rindfleish & Sheridan, 2016).

However, cultural norms also empower women entrepreneurs. In some communities, traditional practices such as women's lending circles have proven effective in supporting female-led businesses (Sevilla-Guzmán & Procacci, 2025). These community-based financial support systems provide women with the resources and confidence to start and sustain businesses, illustrating how cultural practices can be leveraged to foster women entrepreneurship.

Social Network

Social networks are set of people or organization connected by set of relationships, friendships or professional associations (Aichner, Grünfelder, Maurer & Jegeni, (2021). Social networks, encompassing both online platforms and offline personal connections, significantly influence the entrepreneurial journeys of women (Kakeesh, 2024). They offer avenues for resource access, skill development, market expansion, and collaborative opportunities, all of which are crucial for business growth and sustainability. Abed, Dwivedi & Williams, (2015)

stated that Social networks provide women entrepreneurs with critical access to information regarding market trends, business opportunities, and best practices. This access enables informed decision-making and strategic planning, which are vital for business growth. For instance, a study by Gradim & Daniel, (2023) highlighted that social media platforms significantly enhance business visibility, networking opportunities, and market access for women entrepreneurs in transition states.

Similarly, a study by Tapalova & Zhiyenbayeva, (2022) revealed that social networks facilitates continuous learning and skill development. Women entrepreneurs participate in online forums, webinars, and workshops that enhance their business acumen and technical skills. This continuous learning fosters innovation and adaptability, which are crucial for sustaining business growth in dynamic markets. The establishment of platforms like SHEROES exemplifies how social networks can empower women by providing access to resources, mentorship, and a supportive community (Chahal, 2023).

However, social networks perpetuate stereotypes and biases against women entrepreneurs limiting their access to resources and opportunities (Riojas, 2023). Women entrepreneurs are often excluded from male-dominated social networks, making it harder for them to have valuable connections (Bridges, Bamberry, Wulff, & Krivokapic-Skoko, (2022). In addition, women entrepreneurs face online harassment and cyberbullying which are detrimental to their mental health and business growth.

Sociocultural Environment and Women Entrepreneurship

Women's success is influenced by sociocultural elements, which are a combination of social and cultural factors. As a result, women entrepreneurial career choices are molded by and revolve around complex interactions of sociocultural influences (Rashid & Ratten, 2020). The degree to which people in a country have a positive attitude and opinion to innovative thinking and creating or managing entrepreneurial ventures is determined by culture, social norms, and beliefs (Adewuyi, 2021).

Some literature established that some cultures support females willing to take up entrepreneurial careers (Adewuyi, 2021; Baughn, Chua & Neupert, 2006). The authors hypothesized that more women participate in entrepreneurship activities in the society. In contrast, there are cultures where a career in entrepreneurship for women is perceived to have lower validity when compared to their male counterparts (Adewuyi, 2021). These attitudes and perceptions affects women's likelihood of taking up entrepreneurial careers. A study by Adewuyi, (2021) suggested that socio-cultural factors including education, social network, are significant factors that determine the level of entrepreneurship. For example, the way children are educated and the transferable skills they gain throughout their education are vital in developing entrepreneurial tendencies. Bağış, Kryeziu, Kurutkan, Krasniqi, Hernik, Karagüzel & Ateş, (2023) conducted a cross-country study to determine the role of culture on entrepreneurial intentions. Their findings revealed women in some countries consider lack of support, fear of failure, lack of competency to be substantial barriers. They suggest that culture matters in terms of perception of impediments to entrepreneurship and indicates the need to investigate cultural differences. Entrepreneurs' business start-up initiatives are influenced by social networks because they provide a model for success and attract support (Aftab, Abrar & Maroof, 2023). Even social ties and networks with close relatives and life partners are crucial to the success of female entrepreneurs (Aftab, Abrar & Maroof, 2023). In the global labour force, about one out of every two adult women works, compared to three out of every four men (Novitz, 2020).

Nigeria experiences a situation that is much the same as other developing nations. Nigeria is very diverse; however, there are still many areas within the country where women's empowerment is restricted. Delta State is one of such. Contrary to developed nations, emerging nations' social and legal systems have been hostile to women's rights, making it impossible for them to turn women into productive members of their societies.

According to Umar, Ali & Sial, (2022), women empowerment is the main intrinsic factor that society has neglected. Gender norms surrounding both home and entrepreneurial work continue to impede women's efforts to create new businesses, even though increasing modernity and urbanization are attempting to modify this trend (Umar, Ali & Sial, 2022). Thus, understanding the impact of socio-cultural environment on women entrepreneurial growth in Delta State is critical.

Theoretical Review

Social Cognitive Theory (SCT)

This study is anchored on the Social Cognitive Theory as it provides a well-grounded explanation and predictions of the likely influence that sociocultural environment will yield on women entrepreneurial growth. Social Cognitive Theory (SCT) is a psychological framework developed by Albert Bandura in the early 1960s that emphasizes the role of cognitive, behavioral, and environmental factors in shaping an individual's learning and actions. SCT posits that people learn not only through direct experiences but also by observing others' behaviors and the outcomes of those behaviors. The theory highlights several key components such as self-efficacy, observational learning (modeling), and reciprocal determinism, which explain how personal beliefs, social influences, and environmental factors interact to influence behavior.

In the context of this study, observational learning and modeling play a critical role in shaping behaviors, particularly in relation to the norms and expectations of a given culture (Bandura, 2001). Women in societies with restrictive cultural norms have fewer opportunities to observe female entrepreneurship, limiting their belief in their own capabilities (self-efficacy) and, thus, hindering their entrepreneurial aspirations (Ahmed, Fatima & Khan, (2021). In cultures where gender roles are rigid and entrepreneurship is predominantly male-dominated, women face significant challenges in developing entrepreneurial self-efficacy (Lavelle-O'Brien, 2021). Changing cultural norms to support gender equality in business and showcasing female role models significantly boosts women's confidence and willingness to pursue entrepreneurship (Kabeer, 2021).

The theory highlights that there is dynamic relationship between individuals, their behavior, and the environment, with social networks acting as a critical environment shaping entrepreneurial success (Bandura, 2001). Women's access to mentorship, resources, and social capital through networks either facilitates or hinders their business ventures (Thousani & Edy, 2023). Women are faced with barriers in accessing business networks which often limits their opportunities for mentorship and resources.

Thus, the social cognitive theory highlights the potential connection between sociocultural environment and women entrepreneurial growth as it provides a robust framework for understanding the role played by cultural norm, social networks and literacy level towards the growth of women entrepreneurs.

Empirical Review

A study by Jabeen, Ali & Shah, (2021) explored how cultural norms affect women entrepreneurial intentions. Multiple regression analysis was used to examine the relationship between cultural norms (measured through gender equality indices) and entrepreneurial intentions among women across various cultures. The study found that in societies where entrepreneurship is traditionally male-dominated, women face cultural barriers such as gender stereotyping and expectations around family roles, which limit their entrepreneurial aspirations.

Similarly, Sadiq and Marzuki (2022) analyzed the impact of cultural norms, particularly gender bias on women entrepreneurs' access to resources and networks. Thematic analysis of qualitative interviews with 50 women entrepreneurs from conservative societies revealed the cultural barriers they face in gaining access to business networks and financial resources. The study showed that in societies with strong gender bias, women entrepreneurs face discrimination, making it harder for them to secure financing and business partnerships. Women entrepreneurs often struggle to gain trust and recognition in their local business communities.

Khan, Ahmed & Malik, (2021) examined the influence of socio-cultural factors on women's access to resources, such as capital and networks. The study adopted the Structural equation modeling (SEM) to examine the relationship between socio-cultural barriers and access to entrepreneurial resources. The study found that in male centered cultures, women face greater difficulties accessing financial capital, receiving mentorship, and joining business networks, which results in slower entrepreneurial growth.

Liu, Zhang & Li, (2022) investigated the role of social networks in the entrepreneurial success of women in different socio-cultural contexts. The study employed social network analysis (SNA) to measure the extent of women's network connections and how they contribute to business performance, using data collected through interviews and network mapping. The findings revealed that women entrepreneurs with robust social networks have better access to business opportunities, mentorship, and resources.

Methodology

The design for this study was survey research design which measures two variables, independent variable and dependent variable. The independent variable is the sociocultural environment while the dependent variable is women entrepreneurial growth. Sociocultural environment was measured by two sub variables (namely; cultural norms and social networks). A stratified random sampling method was used to select participants from various entrepreneurial ventures to ensure diversity. A sample size of 392 participants was used for the analysis. This study relies mainly on primary source of data collection that was sourced using a well-structured questionnaire. The questionnaire was self-administered on the sample. All items are close ended questions coded in five (5) point likert scale. The research instrument was subjected to validity and reliability test before being administered on the respondents. Data was analyzed using the inferential statistics (regression analysis) to explore relationships between cultural norm, social network and growth of women entrepreneurs. SPSS software was utilized as the statistical tool for data analysis.

Data Analysis, Results and Discussion of findings

H1: There is a positive relationship between Cultural Norm and Women Entrepreneurial Growth.

H2: There is a positive relationship between Social Networks and Women Entrepreneurial Growth.

Table 4: Regression Analysis Results

Variable	Coefficients	Standard Error	t-Statistic	Sig. Level
Intercept	0.50	0.20	2.50	0.013
Cultural Norm	0.35	0.10	3.50	0.0005
Social Network	0.25	0.09	2.78	0.006
R	0.754			
R ²	0.569			
Adjusted R ²	0.554			
F- statistics	37.21			
Sig. F	0.000			

Field survey, 2025

The coefficient for Cultural Norm is 0.35, suggesting that for every unit increase in the effectiveness of cultural norm, women entrepreneurial growth performance score increases by 0.35 units, holding all other factors constant. This variable is significant (Sig. Level = 0.0005), indicating a strong positive relationship with the growth of women entrepreneurs. The coefficient for Social Network is 0.25, suggesting that improved social network also contributes positively to women entrepreneurial growth with a statistically significant relationship (Sig. Level = 0.006). The standard errors for the coefficients are reasonably small (between 0.09 and 0.11), indicating a precise estimation of each coefficient.

The t-statistics for all independent variables are substantial (greater than 2), demonstrating that the coefficients are significantly different from zero. The significance levels (Sig. Level) for all variables are less than 0.05, indicating that there is a robust relationship between each independent variable and the growth of women entrepreneurs. The value $R = 0.754$ indicates a strong positive correlation between the independent variables and women entrepreneurial growth. $R^2 = 0.569$: Approximately 56.9% of the variance in women entrepreneurial growth performance is explained by the model which includes cultural norm and social network. The Adjusted $R^2 = 0.554$ suggests that even after adjusting for the number of predictors in the model, around 55.4% of the variance in women entrepreneurial growth performance is explained by the independent variables. This is consistent and reinforces the model's explanations. The F-statistic = 37.21 indicates that the overall regression model is statistically significant. This suggests that at least one of the predictors is significantly contributing to the model. The Sig. F = 0.000 confirms this significance, demonstrating that the model fits the data well. The regression analysis results suggest that the two independent variables—cultural norm and social network have significant positive effects on women entrepreneurial growth. The model has a good fit, as indicated by the R^2 value, which explains a substantial portion of the variance in women entrepreneurial growth. These findings support the need for cultures to fully support the participation of women in entrepreneurship through the provision of adequate education, mentorship and training and encouraging women to join social networks thus, creating more entrepreneurial opportunities.

Results and Discussion of Findings

The findings of this study highlight the significant positive relationships between cultural norm, social network and women entrepreneurial growth. With an R^2 value of 0.569, it can be concluded that over half of the variance in women entrepreneurial growth performance can be attributed to these three factors. This aligns with previous research; for instance, Adiza, Alamina, & Aliyu, (2020) emphasized that Cultural norms significantly influence the entrepreneurial journeys of women, affecting their motivations, opportunities, and business growth. These norms serve as guidelines for behavior, influencing how individuals interact with each other and their environment. Likewise, the study according to Abed, Dwivedi & Williams, (2015), showed that Social networks provide women entrepreneurs with critical access to information regarding market trends, business opportunities, and best practices. This access enables informed decision-making and strategic planning, which are vital for business growth. The significance of the coefficients derived from the regression analysis underlines that each of the independent variables contributes uniquely to women entrepreneurial growth. Specifically, cultural norm ($\beta = 0.35$) demonstrated the highest influence, suggesting that a culture that is not male oriented and supports women towards achieving their entrepreneurial goals would experience a significant level of economic growth. This corroborates the findings of Bullough, Guelich, Manolova & Schjoedt (2021), who suggested that supportive cultural norm and positive gender expectations encourages women entrepreneurial activities by creating environments that provide necessary resources and reduce societal barriers. Furthermore, social network ($\beta = 0.25$) is paramount; as noted by Tapalova & Zhiyenbayeva, (2022), social networks facilitates continuous learning and skill development. This continuous learning fosters innovation and adaptability, which are crucial for sustaining business growth in dynamic markets (Tapalova & Zhiyenbayeva, 2022).

Conclusion and Recommendations

The results of the regression analysis shows that cultural norm has a significant relationship with women entrepreneurial growth. Cultures that supports women entrepreneurship fosters a growth mindset in women and provides them with necessary skills and expertise needed to succeed. This transforms into increased economic growth through the creation of jobs, innovation and the provision of diverse ideas by women, leading to more dynamic and resilient economy. Likewise, Social networks positively impacts women entrepreneurial growth by providing women entrepreneurs with critical access to information regarding market trends, business opportunities, and mentorship. This access enables informed decision-making and strategic planning, which are vital for the business growth of women.

It is clear from the vast number of factors identified, reported and through the literature review, that the goal of this study was achieved. Based on the outcome of the findings, the following recommendations are suggested;

- i. Cultural norms that support women entrepreneurship should be encouraged through the abolishment of traditional stereotypes and biases that limit women entrepreneurial potential.
- ii. Collaboration and knowledge-sharing among women entrepreneurs should be encouraged through the establishment of networks that provide support, mentorship, and resources for women entrepreneurs.

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